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Digital Marketing and Entrepreneurial Behaviour in Southwest, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study explored the nexus between digital marketing and entrepreneurial behaviour among youth corps members in southwest Nigeria. From this study's broad objective, three specific objectives and research questions were deduced. Exploratory research design was employed. Self-designed questionnaire and executive interview guide were used to obtain data from the recruited respondent. While, convenient sampling procedure was used to select one-hundred and twenty respondents for online google form questionnaire among youth corps members in six southwest states Nigeria. Both descriptive and inferential statistical tools were employed to perform the data analysis. The empirical outcomes revealed that youth corps members under investigation lack digital marketing platforms knowledge for business reasons. Also, the results indicated that experience, family and friends, provision and access of funds, and interest are predictors entrepreneurial behaviour among youth. The result further revealed that digital marketing contributes to youths' entrepreneurial behaviour. The outcomes from the executive interview granted showed that the rapid development experienced in developed countries in the areas of business activities is due to level of adoption of Artificial Intelligence (AI). And that developing societies are experiencing set back in doing business using AI because of weak technical know-how, irregular power supply, lack of infrastructural facilities to use AI, paucity of data, privacy challenge among others. For business to prosper in this developing societies, entrepreneurs need to aware, learn and incorporate interactive features of AI such as Chabot, search engine optimisation, contactless card.

Keywords: Entrepreneur Behaviour, Digitalization, Digital marketing, Artificial Intelligence

INTRODUCTION

Globally, there is paradigm shift in business orientations from tradition means of creating awareness about the products or services to digital era. An improvement in digital marketing gadgets like emerging digital mobile applications or platforms for marketing the products or services afford both existing and potential entrepreneurs' opportunity to create awareness and advance the coverage of their business. The success or otherwise of the embracement of these digital marketing platforms by an entrepreneur is a function of availability and accessibility of relevant technology, structure of the business organisation and environmental variables. This is because, the functional, adaptive and expandable nature of the digital marketing tools could be a necessary condition for promoting businesses virtually but may not be sufficient for business success if there is inadequate understanding of the content, lack of prerequisite skills for handling the gadgets, low quality of the product or service offer, and inability to meet up with customers' expectations as well as inability to compete favourably with counterpart in the same line of business (Eze, *et al.*, 2020). For many years, the Nigerian government has stressed entrepreneurial (in her strategic plan) as a strategy of tackling rising rates of unemployment and poverty.

According to Nigerian unemployment statistics, a great deal of people who finished from colleges and universities have found themselves unable to find white-collar jobs (Rotimis, et al. 2021). This is a major social and economic issue. With a protracted and stressful time of joblessness, unemployed graduates may commit social crimes and injustice. They may become unproductive and redundant when their knowledge and abilities deteriorate, which may have contributed to the nation's economic prosperity. It is upsetting for graduates who devoted time as well as money in education with the hope of finding work following graduation. Despite the nation's wealth of mineral and natural resources, graduates spend time and cash looking for work (Ogwu et al. 2014). Such challenges are exacerbated in part by the 'Nigerian pedagogical system,' which has an essential disconnect between the curriculum framework and the demands of the 21st century.

Specific Objectives

- i. To find out the knowledge of digital marketing functions among corps members in Southwest, Nigeria.
- ii. To find out the factors responsible for demonstration of entrepreneurial behaviour among corps members in Southwest, Nigeria.
- iii. To explore the influence of digital marketing on youth corps members' entrepreneurial behaviour in Southwest, Nigeria.

Research Questions

- i. What is the knowledge of digital marketing functions among corps members in Southwest, Nigeria?
- ii. What are the factors responsible for demonstration of entrepreneurial behaviour among corps members in Southwest, Nigeria?
- iii. What is the influence of digital marketing on youth corps members' entrepreneurial behaviour in Southwest, Nigeria?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Today's Nigeria has a skyrocketing poverty rate. In Nigeria, 112 million people or 70% live on less than \$1 a day (Akanmu, et al. 2018). Nature and the situation that man finds himself in might sometimes force poverty on him. The threat of poverty is currently the most alarming in the nation, and one of the causes of the sudden increase in poverty among individuals has been linked to a lack of entrepreneurial abilities, which can actually foster a sense of self-sufficiency. Perhaps there has never been a better time to comprehend the importance of entrepreneurship as the driving force behind the economic development and progress of all countries than it is right now. This is essential since Nigeria's current economic development is threatened by the high percentage of poverty. Entrepreneurial intents would have a favourable impact on people's behaviour and may motivate people to launch their own enterprises. A similar positive association between intention and planned behaviour was discovered by Farooq (2018), which may hold true for entrepreneurial behaviour as well.

Product information, internet advertising, and marketing via e-mail and mobile devices have historically made up the bulk of digital marketing communication (Omar & Atteya, 2020). Currently, social media provide a platform for businesses to interact with consumers. Businesses use social media to attract clients. Social media is useful at exploring platforms and websites that let users share content instantly, effectively, and fast as well as produce and trade content (Etale and Uranta, 2022). A company can capture a customer's full attention by creating an intriguing blend of visuals, text, and links on its goods and services (Thomas et al. 2022). The use of technology to boost enterprise manufacturing and creative efficiency has resulted in tentative results in a number of companies (Li, et al, 2023), no wonder Agafonova et al., (2022) examine technical changes in advertising that contributes to the growth of the business surroundings through digitalisation procedures. As a consequence of the study, the authors demonstrated that digitalisation processes, including modern marketing activities, are on the rise, as proven by shifts in customer behaviour as a consequence new the emergence of electronic skills and new experiences.

RESEARCH METHOD

This study employed a method of exploratory research. This is because an exploratory study design, according to Sogunro (2015), fosters the blending both qualitative (executive interview) and quantitative (questionnaire) methodologies. In particular, a triangulation-based strategy of gathering appropriate and pertinent data for the investigation. In an exploratory study, however, qualitative data may be obtained before quantitative data and vice versa. (Creswell, 2014; McMillan and Schumacher, 2010)

The fundamental reason for using this approach was the expectation that the benefits of one method of data gathering would outweigh the disadvantages of the opposing method. As a result, triangulation of data sources is simple, boosting the reliability of the findings (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2011). Qualitative methodologies, notably executive interviews, would be used to collect data on the usefulness of digitalisation. To avoid the reuse of ideas, all qualitative responders would not participate in the quantitative component of the design.

Population

All corps members serving in the six (6) states of southwest between January 2023 to August 2023 and executive interview.

Sample and Sampling Techniques

Twenty (20) respondents per state were sampled using convenient sampling technique totalling one-hundred and twenty (120) recruited participants

Instrumentation

A structured questionnaire with several rating scales and an executive interview were utilized to collect data for the study. The research student created the questionnaire. This included understanding of digital advertising, entrepreneurial behavior, and the elements that influence entrepreneurial behavior. The questionnaire was divided into two pieces. Section A dealt with the respondents' demographic information, whereas the following sections were tailored to address the research issues and goals.

Validity of the Instrument

The degree to which a device evaluates what it is meant to measure and operates as intended is referred to as its validity. The instruments employed in this study underwent to content validity assessment, involving both visual and predictive validity, to confirm their validity. The items are laid out in plain language to allow respondents to easily grasp both their content and validity, while they are also rationally and methodically produced in accordance with the study goals and inquiries given to answer in the first chapter. The researchers' supervisor also contributed to the instrument's validity by giving suggestions that were implemented.

Reliability of the Instrument

A research instrument's reliability is defined as the way it performs on multiple tests. While there is bound to be a certain number of inaccuracies the findings of a quality device collected over time tend to stay constant. The shift towards consistency shown in repeated measurements is referred to as reliability. The internal consistency reliability coefficient was calculated using the Cronbach Alpha reliability approach with coefficient at 0.89 and 0.92 for entrepreneurial behavior and digital marketing instruments respectively.

Method of Data Administration and Method of Data Analysis

Quantitative data was obtained via an online questionnaire. An executive interview was employed to gather information from southwest corps members. The quantitative information collected were analysed using inferential as well as descriptive statistics. To meet the research goal, descriptive statistics such as pie charts were used, while inferential statistics were used. Furthermore, for the qualitative component of the obtained data, i.e., executive interview outcomes, content analysis was used.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1.1 Demographic Information of the Respondents

Chart 1: Descriptive Statistics showing the gender of the respondents

Chart 1 indicates that 67.5% of the recruited participants claimed that they were males by gender traits, while 32.5% which is minority were females. However, no participant claimed prefer not to say. Hence, males dominate the recruited participants from the corps members serving in southwest, Nigeria.

Chart 2: Descriptive Statistics showing the age bracket of the respondents

Chart 2 above reveals that 75% of the recruited participants were within the age bracket of 18-24 years of age while the remaining 25% respondents were between 25-30 years of age. This indicates that majority of the corps members recruited in this research work were between 18-24 years of age as shown in the above chart.

Chart 3: Descriptive Statistics showing the marital status of the respondents

Chart 3 above reveals that 73.3% of the recruited participants were single going by their marital status as at the time of serving their father's land, while the remaining 26.7% respondents were married. This indicates that majority of the corps members recruited in this research work were single. Hence, bachelor dominates the recruited respondents in this research work.

Analysis Based on Research Objectives and Questions

Specific Objective 1: To find out the knowledge of digital marketing functions among corps members in Southwest, Nigeria.

Research Questions 1: What is the knowledge of digital marketing functions among corps members in Southwest, Nigeria?

Table 1: Descriptive statistics showing the knowledge of digital marketing functions among corps members in Southwest, Nigeria.

S/N	Items	SA	A	N	D	SD
1.	Find it easy to use digital marketing tools (e.g., the Internet, E-Mail, and Mobile) for conducting my business	11.7%	20%	15%	30%	23.3%
2.	Find it easy to interact with digital marketing tools (e.g., the Internet, E-Mail, and Mobile).	11.7%	15.8%	24.2%	29.2%	19.2%
3.	Interaction with digital marketing is clear and understandable.	19.2%	18.3%	25.8%	25.8%	10.8%
4.	Believe that it is easy to get digital marketing to do what I want to do	13.3%	18.3%	17.5%	39.2%	11.7%
5.	Believe that digital marketing is easy to use.	20%	44.2%	25%	9.2%	1.6%

SA = Strongly Agree, A = Agree, N = Neutral, D = Disagree and SD = Strongly Disagree

Table 1 contained the participants' perspective towards the knowledge of digital marketing functions among corps members in Southwest, Nigeria. The empirical findings indicated that 11.7%, 20%, 15%, 30% and 23.3% of the recruited participants strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree and strongly disagree respectively with the statement that they find it easy to use digital marketing tools (e.g., the Internet, E-Mail, and Mobile) for conducting business. Hence, 53.3% of the corps members recruited in this research work refuted the knowledge of digital marketing for conducting business.

Similarly, 11.7% and 15.8% of the participants strongly agree and agree that they find it easy to interact with digital marketing tools (e.g., the Internet, E-Mail, and Mobile). 24.2% of them were neutral while 29.2% and 19.2% of the respondents disagree and strongly disagree with the proposition. Also, 19.2% and 18.3% of the recruited participants claimed that interaction with digital marketing would be cleared and understandable, if one has the prerequisite skills and knowledge of the such marketing platform, 25.8% of them were neutral while 25.8% and 10.8% disagree and strongly disagree respectively. Moreover, 13.3% and 18.3% of the respondents believe that it is easy to get digital marketing to do what one wants to do, 17.5% of them were neutral while 39.2% and 11.7% of the recruited participants disagree and strongly disagree with the statement. Lastly, 20% and 44.2% participants had a believe that the digital marketing platform would be easy to use if one has adequate and enough knowledge of its usage.

Specific Objective 2: To find out the factors responsible for demonstration of entrepreneurial behaviour among corps members in Southwest, Nigeria.

Research Questions 2: What are the factors responsible for demonstration of entrepreneurial behaviour among corps members in Southwest, Nigeria?

Table 2: Ordinary Least Square Regression Analysis on the factors responsible for demonstration of entrepreneurial behaviour among corps members in Southwest, Nigeria.

	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Beta		
(Constant)	56.937		10.083	0.000
Experience	0.235	0.118	1.017	0.002
Family & Friend	.125	.118	1.019	0.003
Fund	0.515	0.324	3.176	0.002*
Interest	0.415	0.324	3.176	0.002*

a. Dependent Variable: Entrepreneurial Behaviour

* < 0.05 (significant)

The empirical results indicated that personal entrepreneurial experience acquired, role of family and friends, availability of funds, and individual interest in entrepreneurial activity had positive and significant influence on their demonstration of entrepreneurial behaviour with $t(118) = 1.017$; $p = (0.002 < 0.05)$; t

(118) = 1.019; $p = 0.003 < 0.05$; $t(118) = 3.18$ and $p = 0.002 < 0.05$; $t(118) = 3.18$ and $p = 0.002 < 0.05$ respectively. Such that with a unit increase in the experience, there would be a positive and significant increase of 0.235 in their ability to embrace and demonstrate entrepreneurial behaviour.

Also, with a unit increase in the role being played by family and friends, all things being equal, there would be a positive and significant increase of 0.125 enforcing small bussiness using digital platforms. However, with one-unit increase in access to fund by corps members, there would be a noticeable increase in their demonstration of entrepreneurial behaviour by 0.52. Finally, with one-unit increase in corps members' interest in micro business, there is a noticeable increase in demonstration of entrepreneurial behaviour among corps members in Southwest, Nigeria by 0.42.

Specific Objective 3: To explore the influence of digital marketing on youth corps members' entrepreneurial behaviour in Southwest, Nigeria.

Research Questions 3: What is the influence of digital marketing on youth corps members' entrepreneurial behaviour in Southwest, Nigeria?

Table 3: Summary of the regression result showing the influence of digital marketing on youth corps members' entrepreneurial behaviour in Southwest, Nigeria.

a. Model	Unstandardized Coefficients B	Std. Error	Standardized Coefficients Beta	t	Sig.
(Constant)	21.852	5.522	4.687	0.000	31.842
Digital Marketing	0.616	0.162	0.213	3.477	0.002

a. **Dependent Variable:** youth corps members' entrepreneurial behaviour

Table 3 presents the summary of the regression result showing the influence of digital marketing on youth corps members' entrepreneurial behaviour in Southwest, Nigeria. The empirical finding indicates that digital marketing has positive and significant effect on youth corps members' entrepreneurial behaviour as $t(147) = 3.48$ and $p = 0.002 < 0.05$. However, with one-unit increase in digital marketing there is a noticeable positive change of 0.616 of youth corps members towards entrepreneurial behaviour in Southwestern, Nigeria. Furthermore, the beta value of 0.213 revealed that a one average standard deviation rise in digital marketing would result in a 0.213 standard deviation rise in the entrepreneurial behaviour of youth members of the corps in southwestern Nigeria.

Executive Interview Outcomes

S/N	Interview Questions	Responses	Remarks
1.	Do you see digitalisation offering rich opportunities for the global labour market in the near future? If yes, give reason?	Yes, all the recruited respondents for executive interview session concurred that digitisation have inbuilt potential in offering great opportunities for the global markets both currently and in the future. It is inferred from their claim that that authorities are struggling to adapt appropriately to the rapid rate of labour market change caused by digitisation and automated processes, as public measures to safeguard employees lag after this digital shift. For instance, the COVID-19 epidemic has caused a rethinking of the nature of employment and work environments, as well as hastened the transition of government operations and the lives of individuals to online and electronic mediums. Massive systemic shifts are now confronting managers and workers, affecting their future	Positive

		professional lives as well as their neighbourhoods.	
2.	Do you feel that growing of businesses in advanced countries like UK and America surpassed their counterparts in developing societies like Nigeria because of level of adoption of AI? If yes, give instance?	Yes, Digital employees now account for a sizable share of the total labour force in Eastern European countries. This has risen dramatically during the last decade. The technological shift has led to an increase in the proportion of electronic jobs in many industries in Nordic nations such as Denmark, Sweden, Norway, and Finland. The proportion of employment requiring extensive digital skills has recently increased in the United States of America and the United Kingdom respectively.	Positive
3.	What barriers to introduction of AI in entrepreneurial activities do you feel are needed to be addressed in developing societies like Nigeria in the near future?	They claimed that given the relatively poor internet infrastructure, the share of digital employees in African nations such as Nigeria stays low. Other major impediments to the digital economy in Africa include a lack of digital abilities and low access to computers amongst the people. Because of the scarcity of laptops and desktops required for effective involvement in the digital labour market, engagement in the internet-based economy is confined to activities which can be carried out with mobile devices, such as electronic hailing and e-commerce delivery. This means that individuals have fewer opportunity for participating in more significant jobs, such as programming. Lower specialized digital employment, such as labelling and categorizing content, is also out of reach for a large portion of people on the African continent in general, and Nigerian in particular.	Negative
4	Do you believe that it is critical that people especially those into a business to understand AI and its potential applications in the near future? If yes, give brief reason?	Yes, this is the case why technological advances not only alter the number of jobs, but they also impact how work is thought and how individuals do what they do.	Positive
5.	Are there any interactive features of AI that you would like to suggest for potential and existing entrepreneurs in developing societies like Nigeria to add and embrace in the near future?	Yes, they claimed that the effectiveness of AI interactive platforms to enhance business transaction in developing societies like Nigeria depend on the available and accessible digital infrastructure in the society. This is because there are series of AI interactive features can be utilised among the business owners depending on the nature of the business, they engage in.	Positive

CONCLUSION

The empirical results indicated that personal entrepreneurial experience acquired, role of family and friends, availability of funds, and individual interest in entrepreneurial activity had positive and significant influence on their demonstration of entrepreneurial behaviour respectively. Such that with a unit increase in the experience, role of family and friends, availability of funds, and individual interest in entrepreneurial activity there would be a positive and significant increase in the ability to corps members to demonstrate entrepreneurial behaviour using digital platform In a nutshell, financial assistance from a relative may enable an aspiring entrepreneur to have fun with entrepreneurial initiatives. The empirical finding indicates that digital marketing has positive and significant effect on youth corps members' entrepreneurial behaviour.

Recommendations

Digital entrepreneurship education should be provided in developing societies like Nigeria to teach students how to build an enterprise on an online platform and offers an entirely new viewpoint regarding what an entrepreneur way of life entails, how it may be linked to their current way of existence, and how various perspectives must be accounted for in digital educational programs.

The study recommended for those in the marketing field to genuinely comprehend the importance of social media advertising strategies and programs, as well as how to implement them efficiently using performance assessment indicators, in order to improve entrepreneurial behavior among adolescents.

To provide adequate facilities for people to create companies, the government must have fair incentives like taxes, invest in numerous industrial areas, and open economic centers.

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